

ELEMENTARY EDUCATION IN INDIA : ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

Dr. Khemendra Kumar Sharma
(Teacher Educator), Department of Education

Abstract :

The term education explains the concept of all educational field in itself. such as - Elementary education, secondary and Senior Secondary education, Higher or university education. Elementary education is the base of every education. Elementary education is the sensitive and crucial period of one's life, 6 to 14 years of child study in elementary education. The overall development (cognitive-Head, affective - Heart , pshy- motor - Hand) of child is done in this period of life. The history of elementary education is not a new concept. In India the origin of elementary education was started with Vedic era. In Buddhist period, the Gurukul transformed into math and vihara As well as in Muslim period the elementary education was delivered in Madrasa and maktab. After a long period of slavery (British India) get a new structure of education. In that era education divided into three parts (elementary education, secondary and Senior Secondary education, and Higher education) it's also gave many suggestions and recommends over elementary education (woods education dispatch 1854, Hunter commission 1882 , Hartog committee on education 1929, sergeant commission 1944) and so on. In India the ratio of literacy rate for 2018 was 74.34% , we are not achieved the goal of 100% literacy rate. Many causes and challenges are behind this - lack of teacher, funding resources, awareness towards education, defective curriculum, defective administration, problem of language and so on . To improve the quality of elementary education government initiated many programs and schemes (SSA , Midday meal , Read India Grow India) and so on.

Keywords : - Elementary education, Educational policies and programs , literacy rate.

Introduction:-

Education plays a vital role in the human beings life . Without education we can't imagine a developed society or a developed country. only Education which differ us from animal .Education built a man, enhanced its skill , communication power, self confidence and more it's also give him / her ability to adjust in the society as well as cope with new situation, circumstances ,hurdles of life .

Adiguru shankaracharya asked that " Ik Kku ;k foeqDrs " Means That is knowledge, which liberates!!

According to modern philosopher Swami Vivekananda - " Education is the menifestation of perfection, already present in man. "

Elementary education is the foundational stone for every country or society which need changes in life. Because it's paved the way for higher education.

The meaning of Elementary education :-

Elementary education is also known by many other name such as - the root education , foundational education, base education, primary education and so on. The elementary education is begin with the age of 5 or 6 .

1 According to unicef -" It is in primary school that children learn foundation skills that prepare them for life, work and active citizenship. "

2 According to U.N. -" Article 24- Education - " The full development of Human potential and sense of dignity and self- worth and the strengthening of respect for Human rights , fundamental freedom and Human diversity ."

The origin of elementary education in India :-

The origin of elementary education was started with the era of Vedic period. Gradually its progress and many reforms come in this field. In India , education has a rich and exciting history of its development. From Vedic period to British period the elementary education was proceed efficiently. To discuss the origin or history of elementary education, we classified it into four stages . They are as –

1) In Vedic period the elementary education-

In Vedic period the elementary education was held in the "Gurukul ". The Gurukul was the house of the teacher who was a settled house - holder. After the initiation ceremony , a child would leave his natural parents and reside in his receptor , where the students gathered for advanced learning and enriched themselves through discussion and discourses. According to Gurnal mirdal (1898-1987) " Education is the collection of religious work of Veda , mantra, religious book from generation to generation, which based on the rote method of learning".

2) In Buddhist period the elementary education in India –

After the Vedic era ,the influence of Buddhist period was highly on the elementary education. According to F.E.Kenny - " Buddhist education from 500B.C. to 1200A.D. was more prevalent ,adopted that kind of education,which is echo of Brahmin education. But it's also a mirror for many educational institutions."

3) In Muslim or Mediaeval period the elementary education in India –

As in Vedic period upnayana sanskar or in Buddhist period pabbja sanskar was the first ceremony to enter in the elementary education as same in Muslim elementary education, they started it with the Bismillah khawah . This ritual was implied on the child ,when he was 4 year 4 month 4 days .

3) **The elementary education in British India –**

The present system of education was interdicted and founded by the East India company and later ,British India. According to chudhary(2009) - Begining in 1858 ,the crown via British adminstration controlled education policy untill 1919, when education was transferred to the control of Indian ministers at the proviance level. The following recommendations which made **by British period for elementary education –**

1) **woods Education Dispatch (1854) the maagna carta letter :-**

woods education dispatch was the first official document to present National educational policy ,outlined the company's role in providing schooling in British India. Sir Charlas recommend that primary school adopt vernacular langages to teach the students.

2) **Hunter commision (1882) :-**

Lord rippon appointed the Indian education commission on Feburary 3,1882. Under the chairmanship of William Hunter ,a member of the executive council of the viceroy . After studying primary education problems from every angle , the following recommendations : 1) the policy should Encouraged to make students self - dependent .2) Students should be given primary education through the medium of their mother tounge . 3) District boards , municipal boards and town area are responsible for primary schools. 4) Open schools for the training of primary teachers . 3) Hartog commitee on Education 1929- was appointed to review the overall position of education in the country .The commitee felt that primary education was ineffectual because there was a good deal of wastage and stagnation .

4) **The Zakir Hossain 1937and the central advisory board of education in 1938 –**

emphasized the medium of instruction in primary schools. According to both commitees, the medium of instruction should be vernacular or Indian languages.

6) **The second committee of central advisory board of education (1939) and sergent commission (1944)** mentioned that primary education should comprise eight years from the age of 6 to 14 , and divided into two stages (junior basic and senior basic) .

5)**The elementary education in post - independent India : –**

In India education in elementary level is free and compulsory to all children upto age of 6 to 14 years . At the time of adoption of the constitution in 1956 , the aim was to achieve the goal of universalization of elementry education (UEE) within the next ten years by 1960. Many constitutional amendment was taken by Indian government .

1) Article 45- free and compulsory education for all children untill they complete the age of fourteen years, under the article 45 of the directive principles of states .

2) 42nd constitutional amendment 1976 - Before 1976 , education was the exclusive responsibility of the states . With the 42nd constitutional amendment 1976 , education change from being a state subject to a concurrent list subject .

3) The Education commissioner (1964-1966) - Under the chairmanship of Dr. D.S. Kothari , chairman in particular was to advise the government on the National pattern of education and on the general policies for the development of education at all stages ranging from the primary to post - graduate stage and in all its aspects besides examining a host of educational problems in their social and economic context .

6) National policy on Education (NEP) 1986 :- According to NPE, Education is a unique investment in the present and the future. Since the adoption of the Policy on Education in 1968, "there had been a considerable expansion in educational facilities all over the country.

7) Eighty-Sixth Constitutional Amendment Act, 2002 :- The Constitution (Eighty-sixth Amendment) Act, 2002 inserted Article 21-A in the Constitution of India made elementary education a fundamental right, i.e. the State shall provide free and compulsory education of all children in the age group of six to fourteen years as a Fundamental Right in such a manner as the State may, by law, determine.

8) sarv shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) :- SarvaShikshaAbhiyan was started in 2001 is a Government of India's flagship programme for "the achievement of Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) in a time-bound manner, as mandated by 86th Amendment to the Constitution of India making free and compulsory education to the Children of 6-14 years age group, a Fundamental Right .

9) Right Of children to free and compulsory education (Amendment) Act, 2012 :- "Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (Amendment) Act, 2012, which represents the consequential legislation envisaged under Article 21-A, means that every child has a right to full-time elementary education of satisfactory and equitable quality in a formal school which satisfies certain essential norms and standards.

10) National Policy on Education (NPE) 2016 :-New Education Policy 2016 endorsed the revision of No-Detention policy, promotion of Sanskrit, inculcation of values through education, regularity and punctuality in school, cleanliness, self-control, industriousness, and a spirit of entrepreneurship.

11) New Policy on Education (NEP - 2020) :- National Education Policy 2020 has been announced on 29.07.2020. The National Education Policy 2020 proposes various reforms in school education as well as higher education including technical education. A number of action points/activities for implementation in school education are mentioned in the National Education Policy 2020.

The challenges and issues in the field of Elementary Education :-

Education has a significant role in the development of the personality of the child. During the phase of school education, primary education is one of the strong pillars which determine the development of all the faculties of the child. They are familiar yet very important issues and challenges. They are given

- 1. Neglect of Education by the Foreign Rule:-**The British Government needed clerks in India for their commercial establishments and Government offices. So the education system that they introduced in India geared only for producing clerks.
- 2. Political Problems:-**As a result of centuries of exploitation, India's condition at the time of independence was very pathetic. The last blow was inflicted on the country by the British through their policy of divide and rule. Their policy inflamed communal passions in this subcontinent and the Indian leaders.
- 3. Lack of Practical Knowledge in Administrative Policies:** Two main problems related to education cropped up before the country after independence. They are: 1) introduction of compulsory education for the children of 6 to 14 years age group 2) transformation of traditional primary schools into basic ones. Although the first problem of compulsory education was covered in the Constitution, yet due to financial rigidity, the achievement of the fixed target remained impossibility.
- 4. Lack of Teachers:**Scarcity of teachers is a prominent factor in the slow expansion of compulsory education and this is due to poor remunerations.
- 5. Shortage of Funds:**The burden of primary education is being shouldered mostly by local bodies since the British rule. The British adopted this policy simply to misguide Indians, but it is regretted that the same policy is still being followed.
- 6. Defective Educational Administration:**The burden of primary education in almost every State rests on local bodies, that is, on municipal and district boards.
- 7. Defective Curriculum:**The old curriculum of primary schools was defective. It had no scope for the development of the student's creative and constructive faculties nor did it help in acquiring practical knowledge.
- 8. Difficulties in Constructing School Buildings:**It is a complex problem to open schools in villages and unfortunately most of the Indian people live in villages. In this period of financial stringency, the problem of constructing school buildings is a difficult one.
- 9- The Problem of Language:**Like many other problems facing primary education, the one concerning the medium of instruction is also a major one .
- 10 - Geographical Conditions:** India is a country which abounds in rivers, mountains and forests. In the hilly areas the villages are small and scattered at a great distance from each other. Due to shortage of funds it is not possible to open schools in every village.

11- Poverty and Ignorance: Even today the financial condition of the country is not such as to provide full meals and adequate clothing's to each and every citizen. In many homes it is generally against social custom for the womenfolk to earn some money even when the entire family is unable to get two meals a day. Besides, the majority of the people, being ignorant, do not realize the importance of education.

The program and schemes in the field of Elementary Education

With the formulation of National Policy on Education, India initiated a wide range of programs for achieving the goal of UEE through several schematic and Programme interventions, such as

1) Guidelines for use of graded learning manuals in the classroom : –

Books play a very important role in the development of early literacy in children. It is often seen that in our government primary schools, especially for small children, only text books are available for reading, while it is necessary to get meaningful opportunities for reading and writing along with active interactions for learning to read and write.

2) read india grow india :-

Despite the National Curriculum 2005 being made effective under the Right to Education Act 2009, reading and writing in the school curriculum has been largely confined to text books. Most of the teachers believe that their main purpose is to complete the prescribed course material. The Yashpal Committee in its report "Education without Burden" (1993) strongly highlighted the meaningless and monotonous education in Indian schools and the lack of understanding or understanding of children in the classroom. program components 1) Reading and Writing with Comprehension in Elementary Classes 2) Mathematics.

3) Mid Day Meal Scheme- ; प्रधानमंत्री पोषण योजना)Role -

Mid Day Meal on school participation in respect of enrollment of more students and regular attendance of more students has a significant impact. Most children reach school on an empty stomach. Children who eat before coming to school also feel hungry till noon and cannot concentrate. Mid-day meal can also act as a source of "supplementary nutrition" for children and for their healthy development.

4) Education for all campaign (सर्व शिक्षा अभियान) :-

The Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan is being implemented from the year 2000-2001 with the objectives inter alia of universal access and retention, removal of boy-girl and social class differences in elementary education and various interventions to improve the quality of learning. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan is a unique district based decentralized scheme. The scheme is implemented across the country and covers all major government educational initiatives. Under this campaign, a target was set to provide elementary education to all children in the age group of 6-14 years by 2010 with the participation of the states.

Conclusion =

In the above stated paragraph, the elementary education is the base for every field of life . The structure of education (Secondary, Higher, University education) all are stand with the support of elementary education. To achieve the SDG 4th Goal (Quality education) it's mandatory for India to enroll every child (Religion , region, caste , Gender ,economic level) in elementary education without any discrimination. It's our all duties to support and forward the universalization of elementary education (UEE) program. Many causes which challenge the fulfillment of 100% literacy rate of UEE(2000) . Such as lack of trained teacher, awareness and interest of parents for elementary education, lack of funding, construction of School building, lack of administrative infrastructure and so on. To combet this challenges , the Indian government organized many programs on elementary education. There is a famous quotes on education by eminent educationist

" Education is simply the soul of a society ,as it passes from one generation to another generation"

G.k. chesteran .

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